

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES EMPLOYED BY ALGERIAN FIRST-YEAR MIDDLE SCHOOL EFL LEARNERS DURING ORAL INTERVIEWS*

Sarah ABDELHAKIM¹, Nadia ZERROUKI², Yazid MEFTAH³

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Abstract

The present study investigated the oral communication strategies (CSs) used by twelve Algerian First-Year Middle School (1MS) English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners at Riabi Rabah Middle School, Khemis El Khechna, Boumerdes, Algeria, during the later part of the first semester. The participants, who had studied English for three years, answer seven semi-structured oral interview questions. Each interview was allocated up to ten minutes per pupil, audio-recorded, transcribed, and systematically coded and analyzed following the CS taxonomy proposed by Dörnyei and Scott (1997). The results demonstrated that pupils commonly use fillers and hesitation devices, followed by self-repair, message abandonment, code-switching, and approximation. The findings indicated a higher reliance on direct, indirect, and then interactional CSs to maintain spoken interactions despite 1MS EFL learners' communicative difficulties. In order to enhance learners' confidence and oral performance, the findings suggested including CSs education, establishing a supportive learning environment, and further studies that investigate the use of CSs by Algerian EFL learners in large classrooms.

Key words: *Communication strategies, 1 MS EFL learners, Oral interaction, Taxonomy, Algerian Middle School.*

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¹PhD student, Master's degree, TECLANG Laboratory: Department of English: Faculty of Letters and Languages M'hamed Bougara University of Boumerdes (Algeria), Boumerdes, e-mail address: s.abdelhakim@univ-boumerdes.dz, corresponding author, ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1890-4854>

²Associate Professor (MCA), PhD in Linguistics, Department of English: Faculty of Letters and Languages M'hamed Bougara University of Boumerdes (Algeria), e-mail address: na.zerrouki@univ-boumerdes.dz, ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3757-606X>

³Associate Professor (MCA), PhD in Linguistics and Didactics, TECLANG Laboratory: Department of English: Faculty of Letters and Languages M'hamed Bougara University of Boumerdes, Algeria, e-mail address: y.meftah@univ-boumerdes.dz, ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9820-7796>

1. Introduction

For beginner EFL learners, speaking might be considered one of the most challenging skills, particularly when they have limited linguistic resources. Throughout educational transitions, when students should utilize the language in real-life situations, this challenge intensifies. In Algeria, IMS EFL students were required to participate in oral tasks such as interviews and began learning English with minimal prior exposure. As a result, students might frequently use CSs in such contexts to overcome communicative difficulties and sustain engagement.

According to previous studies on English learning in Algerian elementary schools, EFL instruction was mainly conventional, emphasizing pronunciation, teacher-centered, and basic lexis acquisition methods with limited application of learner-centered and communicative approaches (Cheriguene, 2025). Conversely, the middle school syllabus ensured the acquisition of the four skills, including speaking production. Therefore, in educational environments, writing and reading were still frequently given precedence above speaking, which makes oral production even harder for beginner learners (Belit & Aliouchouche, 2021).

As IMS pupils transition from basic English exposure to more sophisticated communicative expectations, these pedagogical factors play an essential role in spoken communicative challenges that they might encounter. Learners used CSs extensively to deal with these obstacles and maintain engagement. In Algeria, researchers were paying greater attention to CSs' studies.

Some of them had focused on CSs' fields within higher education settings, such as Hamlaoui & Haddouche's (2013) research on EFL Algerian students' CSs; Douadi's (2019) study, which examined oral CSs used by EFL Algerian learners to deal with speaking challenges (one of their findings was that several CSs were employed by Algerian young learners during language classes); Zerrouki and Al-Khanji's (2020) study on the effect of task type on the choice and use of communication strategies by Algerian EFL learners in spoken discourse; and Guettal and Bahloul's (2025) research, which discussed how essential it was to explicitly model CSs in EFL training in order to improve learners' interactive skills.

However, few studies had concentrated on CSs' use by beginner learners at the critical phase between primary and middle school in Algeria. Especially since pupils had to adjust to new curriculum demands, teaching strategies, and communication expectations within the first semester of middle school, which was a particularly delicate stage. Actually, Hamadache and Amrani (2022) explored the CSs employed by primary school teachers in the classrooms and how they enhance engagement, whereas Berkati and Ferroudj (2022) investigated the effect of multilingualism on Algerian middle school strategic competence development. Clearly, it appears that no study explicitly examined Algerian IMS EFL learners' CSs use during oral interviews as a distinct research setting.

By analyzing the oral CSs applied by Algerian IMS EFL pupils at Riabi Rabah Middle School in Khemis El Khechna in the latter half of the initial term, the current research sought to bridge this gap. In particular, the following research questions served as the study's compass:

Question 1: What types of oral CSs do Algerian IMS EFL learners employ during oral interviews?

Question 2: Which CSs do these learners most commonly apply?

This study intended to provide empirical insights on the strategic behavior of beginner IMS EFL learners and enhance pedagogical practices for oral production instruction in Algerian middle schools by investigating these questions based on the CS taxonomy proposed by Dörnyei and Scott (1997).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Studies on the Use of CSs

In both pedagogy and research on Second Language Acquisition (SLA), the notion of communicative competence has been crucial. Grammatical, discourse, sociolinguistic, and strategic competence were the four interconnected elements of Canale and Swain's (1980) model of communicative competence. The ability of learners to compensate for communicative challenges and improve communicative competence using both verbal and nonverbal cues was known as "strategic competence." This component was highly valuable for EFL learners, who frequently relied on compensatory strategies to ensure oral interaction due to their limited language resources.

Maleki (2010) expanded on Selinker's (1972) observation that language learners built systematic approaches to handle communication gaps, defining CSs as "an individual" attempt to identify a means to fill the gap between their communication effort and immediately accessible linguistic assets. According to contemporary scholarship, CSs were the intentional or instinctive techniques that learners might employ to overcome difficulties, keep the conversation's flow, and bridge the gap between communication objectives and attainable communication resources, which were all crucial elements of strategic competence and broader communication efficacy (Li, 2025).

Communication researchers had drawn close attention to the critical role that CSs serve in improving the oral performance of foreign language learners. Significant studies had been undertaken on this topic, including studies by Tarone (1981), Dörnyei and Scott (1997), Chou (2024), Ribeiro (2024), and Nash and Contreras (2025). Many researchers in Algeria had investigated CSs, including Douadi (2019); Zerrouki and Al-Khanji (2020); Hamadache and Amrani (2022); and Guettal and Bahloul (2025). While these studies had made significant contributions to EFL learning, none of them focused on IMS EFL learners. As a result, further study was required in this particular field. Particularly, the types and frequency of CSs used by IMS EFL learners during oral communication. Accordingly, this study sought to fill the gap in the existing body of research, as already mentioned, by investigating the CSs employed by Algerian IMS EFL learners during oral communication. Its main aim was to determine the specific types of CSs used and to analyze how frequently they are used. Through this investigation, the study aspired to improve our understanding of the learners' strategic conduct in spoken English.

2.2. Taxonomies of CSs

When linguistic resources were limited, language learners used CSs to overcome communicative difficulties and sustain engagement. According to Canale and Swain (1980), CSs were a fundamental aspect of strategic competence that enabled learners to address interactive challenges and maintain the effectiveness of their message. In a similar vein, CSs were described by Faerch and Kasper (1983) as problem-solving techniques that learners employed when they struggled in conveying the desired meaning in a second or foreign language. Whereas, according to Bialystok (1990), CSs were employed particularly to navigate difficulties that arise during an interaction. Based on previous frameworks, Dörnyei and Scott (1997) provided a thorough taxonomy of CSs that incorporates both psycholinguistic and interactional views. These taxonomies have tremendously improved our knowledge about the way learners navigate linguistic limitations in real-time interactions.

Dörnyei and Scott (1997) classified CSs into three categories. The first category, direct strategies, was used when learners face challenges in communicating and attempt to overcome them directly and immediately, either by avoiding linguistic difficulties or by employing compensating CSs like switching to the first language (L1) or paraphrasing. The following category, indirect strategies, aimed at facilitating interaction by maintaining the flow of interaction and establishing circumstances for equal comprehension; these CSs involved time-saving devices like fillers. Interlocutors cooperate in the third category, known as interactional strategies, which were used to negotiate meaning through CSs like requests for clarification or appeals for help. This comprehensive classification of CSs captured both problem-solving and interaction-management aspects of learners' communication, which makes Dörnyei and Scott's (1997) taxonomy an effective tool for both qualitative and quantitative analysis of learners' speech.

Consequently, the current study adopted pre-existing taxonomies, more specifically Dörnyei and Scott's (1997) taxonomy, as its main analytical framework to investigate the oral CSs used by Algerian IMS EFL learners.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Participants and Ethical Safeguards

The sample consisted of twelve Algerian IMS EFL learners (9 females and 3 males), aged between 11 and 12 years old, enrolled at Riabi Rabah Middle School in Khemis El Khechna in Boumerdes, Algeria. All of the participants were Arabic-speaking learners who had studied English for three consecutive years in primary school. This was their first time experiencing it with the middle school English syllabus. Actually, the sample provided a small, yet representative, sample for an exploratory classroom-based study. Additionally, the first author of the study was the participants' English teacher. As a result, several precautions were taken into consideration to minimize any possible influence and ensure ethical integrity in pupils' responses. To clarify, pupils' identities remained completely anonymous, only aggregate data was reported, and pupils were informed that the participation would not be graded or affect academic evaluation.

3.2. Research Design, Data Collection Tools and Analysis

The researchers aimed at identifying and classifying the oral CSs used by beginner EFL learners during oral interactions. Data collection occurred in November 2025 within regular classroom activities in the latter part of the first semester, a vital transitional phase in which pupils were adjusting to new curriculum demands and teaching methods. In this study, a qualitative analysis complemented by quantitative frequency counts was applied to investigate learners' strategic behaviors following the CS oral taxonomy proposed by Dörnyei and Scott (1997), providing for a thorough evaluation of learners' strategic conduct in spontaneous classroom interactions.

The semi-structured interview served as the primary research instrument to collect data in the oral test, giving learners seven questions (four close-ended and three open-ended questions) that were carefully designed to elicit natural oral output while staying relevant to pupils with limited linguistic competence. Pupils were engaged in natural oral communication, where they talked about themselves (What is your name? How old are you? Are you happy?), their daily habits (What are your daily habits?), preferences (What is your favourite food? Do you like football?), and employed their already-learned vocabulary during the first school term (Look at this picture, please. What do you see?). Each pupil replied individually at the teacher's desk, with a maximum of ten minutes allotted per interview, so the total time for all 12 participants had a maximum duration of 2 hours. However, some learners completed their responses in less time. All sessions were audio-recorded with a Samsung Galaxy S21 FE 5G and then transcribed verbatim. The obtained transcriptions were thoroughly and systematically analyzed following pre-existing taxonomies, mainly Dörnyei and Scott's (1997) oral CSs taxonomy, which allows for the detection, classification, and measurement of verbal CSs, hence facilitating both quantitative and qualitative data analysis.

It is crucial to mention that the researcher performed an intra-rater reliability check to ensure the coding process's dependability. In order to minimize memory bias, the researcher recorded the same data at a sufficient interval after the initial coding of CSs from the interview transcripts was completed. After comparing the two sets of frequency counts, any differences were examined and resolved. This process increased the analysis's credibility and verified the coding scheme's consistency. Descriptive statistical methods were used to answer the study's questions. Percentages and frequencies were used to identify the types of CSs used by learners and to determine which strategies were used more frequently.

Table 1. Type of Communication Strategies Classification Used in the Study

Strategy Category	Strategy Type	Description
Direct Strategies	Circumlocution	Exemplifying, illustrating, or describing the properties of the target object or action.
	Approximation	Using a single alternative lexical item, such as a superordinate or a related term, which shares semantic features with the target word or structure.
	Word Coinage	Creating a non-existing L2 word by applying a supposed L2 rule to an existing L2 word.
	Code-Switching	Including L1/L3 words with L1/L3 pronunciation in L2 speech; this may involve stretches of discourse ranging from single words to whole chunks and even complete turns.
	Self-Repair	Making self-initiated corrections in one's own speech.
	Message reduction (Topic Avoidance)	Reducing the message by avoiding certain language structures or topics considered problematic language-wise, or by leaving out some intended elements for a lack of linguistic resources.
	Message Abandonment	Leaving a message unfinished because of some language difficulty.
Interactional Strategies	Direct Appeal for Help	Turning to the interlocutor for assistance by asking an explicit question concerning a gap in one's L2 knowledge.
	Asking for Clarification	Requesting explanation of an unfamiliar meaning structure.
Indirect Strategies	Asking for Confirmation	Requesting confirmation that one heard or understood something correctly.
	Use of Fillers	Using gambits to fill pauses, to stall, and to gain time in order to keep the communication channel open and maintain discourse at times of difficulty.
	Self-Repetition	Repeating a word or a string of words immediately after they were said.

4. Findings and Discussions

Based on Dörnyei and Scott's (1997) oral CS taxonomy, Table (1) below presents the types, frequency, and percentages of CSs employed by Algerian IMS EFL learners during the oral interview task. The data were collected by transcribing learners' oral productions and identifying the CSs used.

Table 2. CCs Employed by Algerian 1MS EFL Learners During the Interview Task

Strategy Category	Strategy Type	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Direct Strategies	Circumlocution	0	0.00 %	11
	Approximation	6	2.84 %	7
	Word Coinage	0	0.00 %	12
	Code-Switching	11	5.21 %	5
	Self-Repair	18	8.53 %	3
	Message reduction (Topic Avoidance)	51	24.17 %	2
	Message Abandonment	15	7.11%	4
Total	101	47.87 %		
Interactional Strategies	Direct Appeal for Help	8	3.79%	6
	Asking for Clarification	3	1.42 %	9
	Asking for Confirmation	1	0.47 %	10
	Total	12	5.69 %	
Indirect Strategies	Use of Fillers	94	44.55 %	1
	Self-Repetition	4	1.90 %	8
	Total	98	46.45 %	
Total		211	100 %	

4.1. Findings Related to *Question 1*: What types of oral CSs do Algerian 1MS EFL learners employ during oral interviews?

The findings of research question (1) demonstrated that the participants resorted to a wide range of CSs during the oral interview task. Overall, a total of 211 instances of CSs were identified in learners' oral production. Whereas several strategy types were frequently used, others were either rarely used or completely absent, indicating an uneven distribution of strategy use among the participants.

Based on table n°2, 12 types of CSs were used by Algerian 1MS EFL learners, with a total of 211 CSs during the oral interview task. Notably, they employed a substantial number of CSs when communicating in English. Such frequent use of CSs might be particularly pronounced in contexts like Algeria, where classroom instruction often prioritizes accuracy over fluency and learners have few opportunities to practice spoken English outside classroom settings.

More intriguingly, Yahia (2024) investigated the impact of the Arabic language on EFL learners' (Algerian) speaking competence. Arab learners, particularly in Algeria, struggle with L2 speaking due to little exposure and significant linguistic variations between Arabic (including dialects) and English, which made learning especially challenging for beginners. Relating it to our study,

all of this might lead to reliance on a range of strategies such as use of fillers and message reduction (topic avoidance).

The findings also showed that learners used a variety of oral CSs, which were classified into four main categories: direct strategies, interactional strategies, and indirect strategies. The results demonstrated a reliance on direct CSs in the first place with a total of 101 occurrences, followed by indirect CSs (98 instances), while interactional CSs were the least used (12 occurrences). The necessity for 1MS EFL learners to directly overcome lexical communicative difficulties using CSs such as code-switching, self-repair, and message reduction. In order to sustain fluency and gain time during speech production, 1MS EFL learners typically used indirect CSs, including repetition and fillers. Conversely, since the task required greater personalized expression, rather than conversing with another person, it limited the need for confirmation or clarification. This pattern aligned with the present results in the 1MS EFL context, where learners might be concentrating on upholding problem-solving CSs (direct CSs) and fluency CSs (indirect CSs) above participating in active engagement.

In terms of direct strategies, learners mostly relied on message reduction (topic avoidance) (51 occurrences), self-repair (18 occurrences), message abandonment (15 occurrences), code-switching (11 occurrences), and then approximation (6 occurrences), respectively. Notably, word coinage and circumlocution were completely absent from the learners' strategy use.

Dörnyei and Scott (1997) defined message reduction (topic avoidance) as minimizing the message by omitting some planned components due to an absence of linguistic resources or by ignoring specific language structures or subjects deemed linguistically challenging.

For example, *the teacher asks: "Do you like football?"*

One learner says: "Yes." (Instead of: "Yes, I do like football.")

The dominant use of message reduction in the current study reflected patterns identified in earlier research on learners' limitations in strategy use (Faerch & Kasper, 1983; Dörnyei & Scott, 1997; Nakatani, 2010). Accordingly, we could claim that Algerian learners rarely practice the English language in their daily life or in the classrooms, as it is not their L1. In addition, learners' disinterest in the language since it might appear to be challenging for them is a reason that could lead to a low speech level and self-doubt, as well as extremely limited linguistic resources, which result in the high reliance on message reduction (topic avoidance) in oral production.

Another result of table n°2 was the important use of both self-repairs, with 18 occurrences, and message abandonment, with 15 occurrences. Self-repair was referred to as "self-produced speech corrections," whereas "message abandonment" was actually failing to finish a message entirely due to a language barrier, as it is suggested by Dörnyei and Scott (1997), such as in the following examples:

*Learner E claims: "... I am old aaa eleven twelve nts eleven years old."
(Self-Repair)*

Learner A says: "My habits is ..." (falling silent) (Message Abandonment)

In fact, the most important reason for learners' use of these CSs is justified by Dörnyei and Scott (1997), in which they noted that self-repair represents an effort to maintain accuracy, whereas message abandonment occurred when communicative issues were impossible to solve (based on learners' thinking). These findings implied that when learners faced communicative difficulties, they alternated between trying to solve the problem and just withdrawing or avoiding communication.

Dörnyei and Scott (1997) claimed that code-switching includes using the first and third languages (L1/L3) terms in second language (L2) speech, which could be multi-word sequences, complete turns, or single words, and articulating them with L1/L3 pronunciation. Whereas approximation was defined as a strategy in which learners employ a single different lexical item that shares semantical characteristics with the target language word or structure, such as a superordinate or related term. These examples were selected from our corpus to illustrate the approximation and code-switching strategies:

Teacher asks: "What are your daily habits?"

Learner D: "... Arrasm." (drawing) (Code-Switching)

Teacher asks: "What do you see in the picture?"

Learner I: "I see car and aa city ... and aa home." (house) (Approximation)

This result was in line with research on CSs, as Dörnyei and Scott (1997) and Nakatani (2010) claimed, which indicated that low-proficiency learners frequently relied on approximation and code-switching, as these strategies enable participants to express meaning through familial linguistic resources when target language forms were not available. According to recent research, approximation and code-switching were used by 1MS EFL learners (as is the case with the current study's 1MS pupils) to maintain communication and compensate for a lack of target-language resources. Actually, Anshori et al. (2025) agreed that approximation is effective for filling expressive and lexical gaps, particularly for 1MS EFL learners who were less adept. Additionally, Laut and Estremera (2025) claimed that for learners who were facing gaps in their target language proficiency, code-switching provides a flexible means to overcome challenges, understand complex concepts, and maintain communication.

However, circumlocution and word coinage were entirely absent from learners' oral production. Circumlocution (paraphrase) was defined by Dörnyei and Scott (1997) as describing, explaining, and exemplifying a concept when the exact word was unknown, whereas word coinage demonstrates the creation of a new word based on existing language knowledge. Consequently, in the current study, the absence of this pattern might be because learners tend to prefer easily accessible linguistic resources, notably the use of L1 (Arabic) or even L2/L3 (French or the Kabyle dialect in the Algerian context), rather than cognitively demanding CSs like lexical construction or paraphrasing.

Additionally, regarding the interactional strategies, table n°2 showed that direct appeal for help was the most commonly employed strategy (8 instances), followed by asking for clarification (3 occurrences) and asking for confirmation (1

instance). Appeals for help were linked to addressing an explicit query about a knowledge gap in one's L2 in order to obtain assistance from the interlocutor; asking for clarification was asking for an explanation of an unknown semantic structure, while asking for confirmation represented a request to confirm whether one heard or comprehended details accurately, as suggested by Dörnyei and Scott (1997). These were examples selected from the speech of the participants:

Learner C: "aaa kifach nkolo mostashfa b anglais?" (Translated to: "aaa how do we say mostashfa in English?") (Direct Appeal for Help)

Learner K: "Miss hadou dyar?" (Translated to: "Miss are these houses?") (Asking for Confirmation)

Learner K: "Kifash?" (Translated to: "How?") (Asking for Clarification)

IMS EFL learners with limited oral proficiency tend to use simple, basic, low-demand interactional strategies such as direct appeals for help, which might require less linguistic and pragmatic skill than strategies that require asking for confirmation and/or clarification based on recent research in EFL contexts. IMS EFL learners at this academic level, which seemed to be their first year in middle school in which English was not just an introductory subject but rather a core one that aimed at developing communicative competence, might face serious problems during oral production since they might be considered limited-proficiency learners. Logically, since more complex repair initiations required higher pragmatic competence, greater turn-taking abilities, and confidence in communicating, all of which improving IMS EFL learners may lack, lower-proficiency learners tend to avoid them.

In terms of indirect strategies, with 94 instances, the use of fillers was overwhelmingly common. Thus, self-repetition was only used sparingly (4 instances). The use of fillers includes using gambits to fill pauses in addition to gaining time in order to maintain communication's flow when difficulties arise, whereas self-repetition involves the immediate repetition of a word or a sequence of words after they have been produced, as presented by Dörnyei and Scott (1997). For example:

Learner L: "My favourite food is aaa Couscous." (The Use of Fillers)

Learner J: "... I aaa do my homework ... lyy ... aa I do my homework ..." (Self-Repetition)

One way to explain this result was the idea that perhaps due to their limited exposure to spoken English and early stage of language development, Algerian first-year middle school EFL learners tend to use fillers, which indicated the propensity of learners to retain fluency and acquire planning time while engaging in oral production since fillers could be considered simple, approachable CSs that aid learners at this level without interfering with speech. However, self-repetition implied a higher degree of speech awareness and authority over oral production, which inexperienced and beginner learners might still not possess. Consequently,

these learners preferred to select fillers as an even more spontaneous and subtle strategy to tackle mental challenges when communicating.

Overall, when combined, the findings in table n°2 showed that 1MS EFL learners used a variety of CSs to deal with language barriers and sustain oral production during interview tasks. These CSs included fillers and hesitation devices and message-reduction CSs, which enabled learners to maintain the flow of the speech and prevented interaction difficulties in situations where accurate linguistic assets were not easily accessible.

4.2. Findings Related to *Question 2*: Which CSs do these learners most commonly apply?

Based on the findings, interactional CSs demonstrate the lowest percentage, whereas direct CSs contributed the greatest amount, followed by indirect CSs. The prevalence of direct CSs indicated that learners mostly relied on problem-focused and immediate solution approaches when facing communicative barriers. In addition, a significant percentage of CSs were indirect, which reflected 1MS EFL learners' inclination to maintain the flow by utilizing repetition and fillers, providing them with additional time while generating discourse. On the other hand, since the interview focused more on individual speech rather than interaction, the comparatively low percentage of interactive CSs might be justified by limited necessity for meaningful negotiation. This tendency was congruent with the findings of the in-hand study, which might show that 1MS EFL learners relied more on direct and indirect strategies to overcome speech production challenges.

By closely examining table n°2 above, certain CSs were used more frequently than others, with fillers being the most dominant, followed by message reduction (topic avoidance), self-repair, message abandonment, code-switching, direct appeal for help, approximation, self-repetition, asking for clarification, and asking for confirmation, respectively, while circumlocution and word coinage were not adopted at all.

According to table n°2, the results showed that learners made substantial use of indirect communication strategies (46.45 %), particularly the use of fillers, which contributed to 44.55 % of all CSs that were noted. As a result, fillers were by far the most commonly used strategy. Given how frequently they occur, it was likely that learners often used hesitation devices, such as pauses, hesitation sounds, and discourse indicators, to keep their speech plans fluid and dominate the discussion basis. The results of the present study were consistent with the results concluded by Yonata and Saptani (2019), which indicated that "filler was the most frequent strategy used by speakers," and they justified it by learners' difficulty in expressing their ideas verbally as a result of inadequate practice.

At 24.17 %, message reduction (topic avoidance) was the second most common strategy. This suggested that rather than completely reformulating their intended message, learners often reduced or removed parts of it when they encountered lexical or syntactic difficulties. Since condensing the message required less cognitive work than looking for different terminology or patterns, this tendency probably affects real-time processing demand and constrained linguistic resources.

In addition, it allowed learners to remain on topic and avoid mistakes or errors, enabling them to put confidence and fluency over completeness.

Among the direct strategies (47.87 %), self-repair ranked third (8.53 %), indicating that learners frequently identified and fixed their own mistakes when speaking. The increased metalinguistic awareness of learners and their eagerness to communicate accurately and straightforwardly, particularly in task-based (the interview task in the current study) or supervised circumstances, might be used to justify this relatively high reliance. It was followed by message abandonment (7.11 %) and code-switching (5.21 %), indicating that certain pupils preferred to switch to their L1 or ceased an utterance midway when problems could not be promptly handled. Consequently, this might highlight how learners tended to rely on avoidance strategies (such as reduction and abandonment) when they had insufficient linguistic resources and shifted toward more advantageous strategies (such as repair and compensatory ones) as their ability to communicate developed. Additionally, when learners struggled to completely express themselves, code-switching might be used as a way to handle gaps in the target language (TL) and promote engagement.

With direct appeals for help at 3.79 %, asking for clarification at 1.42 %, and asking for confirmation at just 0.47 %, interactive CSs were relatively less frequent (5.69 %), indicating that learners favored internal coping strategies over interaction-based problem-solving. This trend might be explained by the fact that many learners tried to keep conversational control and refrain from showing signs of difficulties in public, particularly in performance or assessment contexts. In fact, using interaction CSs requires confidence, pragmatic competence, and openness to depend on interlocutors, which might be necessary for employing engaging CSs. Furthermore, classroom settings frequently placed a high value upon learners' achievement and fluency, which made learners rely more on self-repair, avoidance, and reduction CSs than on negotiating CSs. Consequently, rather than starting conversations for clarification or confirmation, learners typically handled issues on their own.

Lastly, there was no use of circumlocution or word coinage, suggesting a low dependence on innovative lexical compensatory CSs. These results went along with the results concluded by Zerrouki and Al-Khanji (2021), which claimed that word coinage and circumlocution were the least frequent used among the total number of CSs employed by the Algerian learners. This might be justified by learners' limited vocabulary and insufficient strategic instruction in creative linguistic ability and paraphrasing, which might be generally linked to higher levels of performance. As learners had to define unfamiliar terms or create approximations in real time, these CSs required adaptable language assets and confidence in language manipulation. As a result, many students instead favored safer and easier CSs that demanded fewer complications and mental work, such as abandonment, code-switching, and reduction, when they were facing time constraints. Therefore, the lack of these creative CSs implied that in situations when dealing with lexical gaps, learners accorded fluency and accuracy maintenance precedence over innovative communication. It is important to mention that, since they were employed marginally, other CSs, including both approximation (2.84

%) and self-repetition (1.90 %), did not constitute prominent CSs among the learners, which might be attributed to IMS EFL learners' limited lexical resources.

To recap, it might be said that IMS EFL learners mostly relied on fillers to sustain the communication flow while encountering linguistic challenges in addition to message reduction. Strategies that demand rapid self-monitoring, such as self-repair and message abandonment, also showed with noteworthy frequency, but interactional support strategies were used very seldom. Conversely, more mentally challenging compensating CSs like circumlocution and word coinage were completely absent, demonstrating a preference for easier, less complicated coping CSs over creative linguistic problem-solving throughout the interview task.

5. Conclusion, Implications, and Recommendations

This study examined the oral CSs used by Algerian IMS EFL learners during the oral interview task. The data revealed that learners employed a variety of CSs, which might have contributed to their limited proficiency in the English language. While CSs such as circumlocution and word coinage were completely absent, learners mostly relied on fillers, message reduction, self-repair, and message abandonment. This result suggested that IMS EFL learners tended to reduce or disregard communication rather than seek innovative reformulation, indicating poor strategic competence and limited linguistic resources at this early stage of language learning. Particularly, the high frequency of fillers suggested that learners relied on low-effort CSs to extend their planning time and keep the conversation flowing. These results underlined the necessity of emphasizing explicit training in CSs' use from a pedagogical standpoint. Actually, in order to aid IMS EFL learners and deal with communicative challenges in the TL more effectively, teachers were urged to help them become more aware of direct and indirect CSs and to offer supervised instruction. This kind of training might improve learners' strategic competence and lessen their excessive dependence on avoidance CSs. As a result, it could be recommended that future studies investigate the use of CSs by Algerian EFL learners in large classrooms with a range of tasks, levels of proficiency, and learning contexts, as well as establish a CS training program and a supportive CS learning environment.

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